

Synthesis, Characterisation and Spectral Studies of some Lanthanide Complexes with *p*-(Methoxy or Chloro)phenylglyoxal Thiosemicarbazone

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Lanthanides form coordination compounds with a number of ligands containing nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur as donor atoms¹. Ligands containing sulphur² as donor atom are powerful chelating agents due to the high charge on lanthanide ion which could only be stabilised by highly electronegative atoms of the ligands. A number of lanthanide(III)-Schiff base complexes³ have been reported in literature.

The present work deals with the synthesis of trivalent Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy and Yb complexes of *p*-methoxyphenylglyoxal thiosemicarbazone (PMPGT) and *p*-chlorophenylglyoxal thiosemicarbazone (PCPGT).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of all the complexes indicate 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry (Table 1). These solid

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LANTHANIDE(III) COMPLEXES OF PMPGT AND PCPGT

Compd./ (Colour, m.p. °C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						μ_{eff} BM
	C	H	N	S	Cl	Ln	
C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S (PMPGT) (Brown, 165)	50.53 (50.61)	4.64 4.68	17.73 17.71	13.41 13.48	— —	— —	—
C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI (PCPGT) (Brown, 154)	45.68 (44.72)	3.28 3.34	17.35 17.39	13.21 13.24	14.65 14.67	— —	—
[La(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Grey, 175)	38.38 (38.41)	4.05 4.01	10.71 10.75	8.15 8.20	— —	17.71 17.77	Diamag.
[La(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, 190)	34.88 (34.95)	3.09 3.19	10.58 10.63	8.09 8.11	8.92 8.97	17.51 17.57	Diamag
[Pr(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Grey, 180)	38.25 (38.31)	3.90 3.99	10.68 10.72	8.10 8.18	— —	17.92 17.98	3.48
[Pr(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >195)	34.80 (34.86)	3.15 3.19	10.57 10.61	8.18 8.09	8.87 8.95	17.71 17.78	3.40
[Nd(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Grey, 190)	38.10 (38.15)	3.92 3.98	10.61 10.68	8.05 8.15	— —	18.29 18.33	3.65
[Nd(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, 180)	34.75 (34.71)	3.12 3.17	10.51 10.56	8.58 8.06	8.82 8.91	18.02 18.13	3.72
[Sm(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Grey, 185)	37.81 (37.86)	3.92 3.95	10.53 10.59	8.01 8.08	— —	18.90 18.96	1.52
[Sm(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >200)	34.40 (34.45)	3.10 3.15	10.42 10.48	7.91 7.99	8.78 8.84	18.71 18.75	1.58
[Eu(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, 186)	37.72 (37.78)	3.08 3.94	10.51 10.58	8.02 8.07	— —	19.08 19.13	3.18
[Eu(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Grey, 180)	34.45 (34.38)	3.08 3.14	10.42 10.46	7.91 7.98	8.80 8.83	18.87 18.92	3.52
[Gd(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >198)	37.49 (37.53)	3.87 3.91	10.43 10.51	8.09 8.01	— —	19.58 19.66	7.91
[Gd(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >198)	34.07 (34.15)	3.03 3.12	10.31 10.39	7.91 7.93	8.72 8.77	19.40 19.44	7.85
[Tb(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >200)	37.35 (37.45)	3.82 3.91	10.42 10.49	7.90 7.99	— —	19.73 19.82	9.41
[Tb(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >200)	34.01 (34.08)	3.01 3.12	10.33 10.37	7.82 7.91	8.68 8.75	19.53 19.61	9.55
[Dy(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Grey, >200)	37.17 (37.29)	3.82 3.89	10.40 10.44	7.88 7.96	— —	20.12 20.18	10.71
[Dy(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, >200)	33.89 (33.93)	3.04 3.10	10.24 10.33	7.89 7.88	8.65 8.71	19.92 19.96	10.58
[Yb(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, 190)	36.72 (36.80)	3.75 3.84	10.23 10.30	7.82 7.86	— —	21.15 21.21	4.53
[Yb(C ₉ H ₈ ON ₃ SCI) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂](CH ₃ COO) (Brown, 196)	33.55 (33.49)	3.09 3.06	10.12 10.19	7.90 7.99	8.51 8.60	20.92 20.98	4.40

coloured complexes have high melting points and are soluble in acetone, dioxane, DMF and DMSO.

The observed magnetic moments of the complexes (Table 1) are in good agreement with the theoretical values calculated from the Van Vleck formula⁴. All the complexes except La^{III} are paramagnetic.

The electronic spectral data of the Pr, Nd and Sm complexes (Table 2) exhibited red-shifts⁵ with respect to aquo ions. This is a consequence of complex formation found in many lanthanide complexes⁶. The red-shifts have been ascribed to nephelauxetic effect⁷ resulting from the changes in the inter-electronic repulsion parameters of the complexes. The values of nephelauxetic ratio (β)⁷, bonding parameter ($b^{1/2}$)⁸, Sinha's parameter ($\delta\%$)⁶ and covalency angular overlap parameter (η)⁹ have been calculated. In these complexes the value of β is less than unity while the values of $\delta\%$ and $b^{1/2}$ are positive indicating the covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond¹⁰.

In the ir spectra of the ligands¹¹ PMPGT ($C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3S$) and PCPGT ($C_9H_8ON_3S$), the $\nu_{C=S}$ band appears at 860 and 820 cm^{-1} respectively. Shifting of these bands by 5–45 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicates the coordination of the ligands through sulphur atom of the thiocarbamide moiety. The bands assignable to the $\nu_{as} NH_2$ and $\nu_s NH_2$ are present at 3 440, 3 420 and 3 200 and 3 180 cm^{-1} in the free ligands. These bands are also observed in the case of complexes, indicating that the free NH_2 group of the ligands does not take part in complex-

ation but the decrease in these frequencies may be due to increased positive charge on the N-atom due to donation of the electron pair from S-atoms of the amidic moieties of the ligands to the metal. It further indicates the coordination of ligands through S-atom of the C=S linkage.

The shift of $\nu_{C=N}$ mode of the free ligands at 1 618 and 1 590 cm^{-1} in PMPGT and PCPGT respectively, to the lower wavenumbers by 5–42 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicates the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. This is further supported by the shifting of ν_{N-N} modes of the free ligands (1 050 and 1 085 cm^{-1}) in the complexes¹². The bands at 1 680 and 1 675 cm^{-1} (C=O) in the free ligands do not show appreciable shift in the complexes, indicating the noninvolvement of carbonyl oxygen of the glyoxalic moiety of the ligands in coordination.

The new bands in the spectra of the complexes at 510–475 and 420–370 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of M–N and M–S bonds¹³. In the lanthanide complexes, the bands at 1 520–1 450 and 1 425–1 360 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ and $\nu_s(COO^-)$ modes respectively, of acetate groups, indicate the presence of acetate group in coordination sphere.

Experimental

Lanthanide chlorides (Indian Rare Earths Udyogmandal, 99.99% purity) was used as such. Rest of the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. *p*-Methoxyphenylglyoxal and *p*-chlorophenylglyoxal were prepared by standard method¹⁴. The ligands PMPGT ($C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_3S$) and PCPGT

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} AND Sm^{III} COMPLEXES OF PMPGT AND PCPGT*

Ion	λ_{max} cm ⁻¹	Assignment	β	$b^{1/2}$	$\delta\%$	η
Pr ^{III}	16 807	$^3H_4 \rightarrow ^1D_2$	0.991 6	0.064 8	0.85	0.004 2
	(16 670)		(0.983 6)	(0.090 6)	(1.66)	(0.003 2)
	20 619	$\rightarrow ^3P_0$				
	(20 410)					
Nd ^{III}	22 466	$\rightarrow ^3P_2$				
	(22 222)					
	11 299	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	0.994 3	0.053 4	0.57	0.002 9
	(11 236)		(0.988 7)	(0.075 1)	(1.14)	(0.005 7)
	12 422	$\rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}$				
	(12 494)					
	13 245	$\rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$				
	(13 158)					
	14 599	$\rightarrow ^4F_{9/2}$				
	(14 493)					
Sm ^{III}	16 807	$\rightarrow ^4G_{7/2}$				
	(16 949)					
	19 417	$\rightarrow ^4G_{9/2}$				
	(19 231)					
	21 505	$^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}$	0.999 1	0.021 2	0.09	0.004 5
	(21 276)		(0.988 4)	(0.076 2)	(1.17)	(0.005 8)
	23 868	$\rightarrow ^4I_{5/2}$				
(24 094)						
25 317	$\rightarrow ^6P_{3/2}$					
(25 360)						

* Values in parantheses are those of the PCPGT-complexes.

(C₉H₅ON₃SCl) were synthesised by refluxing *p*-methoxyphenylglyoxal and *p*-chlorophenylglyoxal with thiosemicarbazide (1 : 1 ratio) in absolute alcohol for ~ 4 h and recrystallising the product from ethanol. A general method was used for the preparation of all the lanthanide(III) complexes.

Preparation of complexes General method : To an ethanolic solution of lanthanide(III) chloride (2.5 mmol) was added an ethanolic solution of sodium acetate trihydrate (1.02 g, 7.5 mmol). The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate added to an ethanolic solution of the ligand (5 mmol). The mixture refluxed for 3 h, the excess solvent was then removed by distillation and the remaining solution kept overnight. The separated solid complex was washed with ethanol and dried in air.

The microanalysis for C and H was done by a Thomas CH35 analyser. Halogen and sulphur were estimated by standard methods¹⁵ and nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. The percentage of lanthanide metal was estimated by heating to oxide, then dissolved in 50% HCl and the resulting solution was titrated with EDTA using xylenol as indicator. The magnetic moment was measured at room temperature using Gouy's balance. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Toshniwal spectronic-20D spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer-577 spectrophotometer.

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